

Short name	Accounting Readiness	Long name	Readiness of the national GHG inventory responsible office
Geographical scope	All regions		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>Accurate and transparent GHG inventories at national levels are crucial for tracking progress towards emissions reduction targets and informing climate policy decisions. A robust inventory system helps ensure that countries are held accountable for their emissions and can lead to increased trust and cooperation in international climate negotiations.</p> <p>It also helps to identify areas where emissions reduction efforts can be targeted most effectively.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<p>Expert judgment based on the following factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - previous engagement on CCS-related accounting questions - overall quality of previous GHG inventory reports including accuracy, completeness, comparability, transparency, and consistency over time 		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Liability in Hubs - Accounting of leakage - Accounting of DACS - Accounting of BECCS 		